

beyond
the **third wave**

Chintha Munasinghe

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“I was watching the TV with my legs shivering and my ears echoing, not knowing what was happening. My mobile phone constantly repeating...”the line cannot be contacted right now... please dial later” ... I started sending SMS messages to my colleagues down their in the South with no response. So much forgotten... so much to do... but none has been achieved... Amidst the confusion, I never ever imagined that my brother was caught in the tide, but worried why he has not responded to my SMS... Had no clue whether my father-in-law reached home or not... But, by 27th of December 2004, we were back in the office working out plans to help those who were affected, while my field team was busily involved in helping those severely affected by Tsunami and cleaning the debris. It was at that time, I was contacted by Dr. Ekanayaka and Dr. Liyanage requesting us to involve in helping the people in grief. From then onwards we are with them, struggling with courage to regain the lost hope”.

*Chintha Munasinghe
Country Programme Manager,
BasicNeeds-Sri Lanka*

Invited by Health Administrators in the Southern Province, BasicNeeds Sri Lanka launched its development oriented psychosocial interventions since 30 December 2004. This programme caters to the *Reconstruction of Human Minds to Rebuild the Lives of people affected by Tsunami* in highly affected areas of the southern costal belt selected by the Primary Health Care staff as Tissamaharama, Weligama, Ambalantota, Tangalle, Dikwella and Hambantota MOH areas.

Our interventions are designed in consultation with affected communities, by a team of community development practitioners and mental health/health professionals who intervened on behalf of the Tsunami affected communities in southern Sri Lanka at the onset of the event. The success of the work so far is due to the challenging role performed by the community animators with the background of community mental health aspects, which in turn animated the affected communities experiencing grief due to losses to take an active part in regaining their life.

This booklet will take you through the journey that we, along with the communities in grief were going through soon after the Tsunami struck our island destroying two third of our coastal line taking the lives of about 40,000 people and leaving more than 300,000 displaced.

preparing the work force

(January – Mid
February 2005)

On 30 December 2004 a team of Mental Health Professionals from Mental Hospital Angoda led by Consultant Psychiatrist, Dr. Neil Fernando joined BasicNeeds to visit 08 Camps in Hambantota and Matara to assess the mental health status of children and adults who were in grief after great loss to their families and to recommend the interventions to BasicNeeds in getting them overcome their grief.

STEP 1 - Initial Assessment Visit by Mental Health Professionals:

The team noticed many things: Majority of the people were in the stage of numbness, with no feelings at all. Despite many generous people reaching the camps with many things to serve them with, those who were affected severely and in grief were interested in standing on a queue to receive the donations. Lost assets varied from close relatives to livelihoods, but the grief did not vary. For instance, many school children were crying over their school note books being the most valuable asset in their case. With the volume of people in grief found to be so high, the capacity of individual counselling was questionable. It was similar to a funeral house in a community where people are in grief, the only difference being that it was a mass funeral, where some did not have the bodies of their lost ones to weep over and recover from grief.

At the end of this professional assessment, the team concluded it as a mass funeral where grief counselling at individual level is impractical and not yet needed. As an alternative the psychiatrists recommended that community workers, i.e. community volunteers of BasicNeeds¹ Mental Health and Development programme could play a greater role in providing emotional support (in place of counselling) using traditional practices in helping the affected people to progress towards rebuilding their lives. A crash course to assist traumatized communities, was designed to help these community volunteers to proceed with their duties.

1. BasicNeeds Mental Health and Development programme already being implemented at the time when Tsunami struck, has 123 community volunteers trained in mental health care aspects with more than 3 years experience in providing care for severely ill mental patients in their villages.

When we reached a camp established at Matara Rahula Vidyalaya, I found children sitting in isolation with blank faces, sitting closer to their relatives. But, I noticed a child about 8 years old, sitting under a tree having no contact with anyone. One of my team members went towards him and handed over a drawing book and pastels. He grabbed the stuff, without even having to see who has offered him the book. Next instance, he started drawing without raising his head... and it was nothing but, how the Tsunami tide caught them. We let him draw, and with many children approaching us at the time, we made it possible for everyone who was interested to draw whatever they like to draw. But, all of them had only one thing to draw and it was only TSUNAMI.

*- Dr. Neil Fernando,
Consultant Psychiatrist, Mental
Hospital, Angoda*

Based on the observations and needs expressed by people and children at mental health professionals' assessments visit, a training programme was developed to train 76 village volunteers and 12 staff members from BasicNeeds and its partners. This intensive training programme included both theory sessions and field assignments, which were organised in the camp environments followed by feedback sessions where the participants were encouraged to share their experiences and clarify doubts in practicing what they have learnt. At the end of the programme, a team of 82 community animators was formed, well-equipped with knowledge and skill for building the confidence of communities affected by Tsunami while having the ability to identify high risk groups who need professional assistance in mental health care.

STEP 2 – Four Day Practical Training on How to Respond to the Immediate Psychosocial Needs of Communities affected by Tsunami for community workers:

The 6-day training programme covered themes like Understanding Grief; Active Listening; Problem Solving techniques; Animation techniques; Identification of High Risk Groups. After the training programme the trainees formed 12 teams of 6-members, each comprising a lead animator, group animators, a process writer and a staff member. Each team took charge of 4-5 camps, identified by primary health care workers as most-affected communities.

Having established teams of community animators to consult the affected communities, next responsibility of BasicNeeds and its partners was to identify those who were approached by either a few or no organisations at all in the provision of psycho social care. BasicNeeds held one day workshops for primary health care workers from Hambantota and Matara districts i) to identify the project locations and plan ways to approach communities in grief; ii) to help them de-traumatise themselves from what they were experiencing since December 27, 2004 having called for duty. Some of them were also affected by Tsunami, though they were working for the rescue of others. At the end of these workshops 56 locations were identified in both the districts covering 6 MOH areas. Dates and logistics regarding Community Consultations were agreed and primary health care workers took charge of informing and introducing community animators to camp organising committees.

STEP 3: Consulting Primary Health Care Workers of the Ministry of Health:

BasicNeeds approach to provision of psychosocial care to communities affected by Tsunami consists of a strong (though informal) partnership with the Ministry of Health. While strengthening the capacity of primary health care workers in approaching people in grief, BasicNeeds used the expertise of Psychiatrists assigned by the government as well, in community animator training programmes.

BasicNeeds, its partners and community animators also played the role of service brokers who linked mental health services with the communities, especially in the provision of specialised services to those who come under high risk groups:

- People who have lost all or majority of their close relatives (571)
- Children who have lost both parents (85)
- Single parents with infants or pre-school aged children (223)
- People experiencing mental illnesses (381)
- People with disabilities (342)
- Pregnant and lactating women (1,152)
- Elderly persons above 60 years (1,544)
- People with chronic illnesses (1,198)
- Youth and children taking drugs or alcohol (41)
- Women and children vulnerable to abuse and exploitation (10)

Note: The above figures covered the numbers identified during the period March – December 2005.

let's face the challenge ahead

(January – May
2005)

Community Consultations:

With all preparations completed, 12 teams of community animators approached camps and resettled communities in temporary huts assisted by primary health care workers. By the time people were fed-up with filling forms/questionnaires for nothing. Other than the relief workers and magnanimous locals who came down to donate material or food stuff, people were not interested in anything.

Our teams noticed that the people who were in grief were not interested in even getting those donated items. Mountains of clothing were found lying on the corridors of many schools where the camps were held. Greatly disturbed about their future, people were observed to be getting registered for accessing houses, livelihood equipments, etc. Children looked isolated with no interest in playing. This was the environment in many instances experienced by the community animators, prior to our Consultation Workshops. Having managed to become friendly with a few strong members and with the assistance from Organising Committees in the camp, community animator teams finally were able to gather groups of 50 – 150 people to involve in one-day workshops.

Community animators adjusted the day's programme according to the context and environment of each camp. Where there were more children the team assigned one or two animators to work with them in using "Drawings" as the media to express their feelings and preparing them towards getting rid of their fears. While the children got settled, adults were consulted to select the best location to hold the consultation workshop. In some cases an outside shaded areas were selected while some selected the central part of a hall where they were living.

Children engaged in drawing and expressing their stories without forcing them to do so

When we entered the camp, it was quite disturbing to see that people were on strike against the organising committee of the camp. The public health instructor who was supposed to introduce us to them warned us “Try to finish your work as early as possible and leave the place as it is going to be dangerous.” We saw a group of disturbed youngsters shouting and trying to create trouble. Looking at them we were waiting without making any attempts to disturb them. After a few minutes, a boy approached us and asked the purpose of our visit. He also complained and explained to us about the purpose of their picketing movement. Having understood our purpose for the day, he communicated with his friends and they organised the people for participating at the consultation workshop. They also joined the volunteer committee at the end of the workshop.

- A P Jayarathne, BasicNeeds Associate

Initial Consultation Workshops with Displaced Communities

TOPIC GUIDE 1

- Setting up the environment
- Note: When the animators reached the location, people being so disturbed were not ready to receive them or for participating at a workshop as in a normal situation.
- Religious Observances
- Purpose of the day & the programme (lead animator)
- Self-introductions:
Understanding each other
(Sharing the grief through self introductions/
individual meetings &
special media – drawings,
poems, etc.,)
- Ex. 1: Expressing problems
& proposing solutions in
groups (women, men,
children, youth)
- Group presentations
- Formation of a Volunteer
Committee
- Ex. 2: Assessing family
needs & identifying
families of high risk groups
(Questionnaire filling in
family units)
- De-briefing

Key part of the workshop dealt with getting to know each other providing space for community members to share their grief. This exercise helps them feel that it is not just them who got affected. This is done after setting the environment comfortable for them to relate their stories as an opportunity to relieve their pain. While adults were engaged in this exercise children were engaged in art and music therapy sessions describing their experiences, feelings and experiences. Community animators who were trained in active listening gave individual attention to people who were reluctant to express their feelings in front of other community members. When they noticed children or adults who require psychiatry inputs, they referred them immediately to the psychiatrists and mental health experts who offered mobile service during consultation time.

Children joined the main workshop at tea time exhibiting their drawings and talents. This gave flavour to the event, while building a sign of hope amongst many participants and for a moment they had forgotten Tsunami. That was the time the lead animator explained the purpose of the programme:

Good Morning! You may wonder why we are here today. There are many organisations visiting you these days and as someone mentioned, many asked you to fill forms and vanish. We do not blame you if you have the same attitude towards us, as it is not your fault. Let me be frank and explain to you why we are here. Our team comprising members of BasicNeeds, Navajeevana, GIDES, Divisional Secretariat of Embilipitiya, Ministry of Health and village volunteer committees from the villages we work with are not affected by Tsunami. Together we thought, it is our duty to go along with you sharing the pain and the wealth we possess to face the challenge of re-building our lost lives. Today, we would like you to identify all the problems ahead of us and then work out interventions to address them. From then on, together let's proceed towards achieving what we plan today!
- Lead Animator, Presenting the objective of the day

Interestingly, people tended to show interest in participating at the workshop after describing the purpose of the day followed by a clarification session. It was also observed that majority of the participants were women who were keen to share their feelings openly. Giving the opportunity for anyone to join the group any time of the day has facilitated high participation of people in small group sessions, where problems were discussed and solutions were proposed. Group sessions were organised requesting the participants to get themselves divided into groups of women, men, girls, boys, elderly women, men and children. All the groups were asked to write down the problems they were facing and then propose solutions or interventions to address those. After completing the task each group presented their findings and recommendations to the main group.

With people getting on identifying their problems and working out solutions, we observed the momentum gaining with a hope in their mind for a life that that they consider as useless in many cases. That led them voluntarily join the force of taking the lead as volunteers for supporting our programme.

Thus, from all the 56 communities consulted, there was a volunteer committee formed before the participants broke for lunch. Today we have 368 active volunteers from those affected communities who take charge of:

- Linking and coordinating service providers at community level
- Community awareness on activities planned under our programme
- Identification of high-risk groups and inform/referral
- Providing care and emotional support
- Assisting 6-member team & service providers to plan interventions
- Organise and conduct community reviews against the proposed plans during consultations

Through this methodology of consulting affected communities we were able to consult 5,189 families in 56 locations within 2 weeks. Interestingly, the programme for each community was evolved for psychosocial interventions from the communities themselves.

building blocks of hope

After consulting 56 displaced communities, the community animators and the project team got together to work out interventions and identify the key areas that we should focus on. Thus, it was obvious that our role in “helping Tsunami affected communities to help themselves”, involved three areas of interventions:

- Promotion and provision of mental health services complementary to the government programme
- co-ordination and establishing links between service providers and affected communities in the areas we are in operation and
- Community-led special projects/activities to overcome issues/problems identified by the affected communities as a measure to build their confidence and accelerating their normalisation process.

These proposals were then shared with the volunteers from Tsunami affected communities who confirmed those as the key areas of our involvement.

Promotion and provision of mental health services complementary to the government programme:

Soon after the Tsunami there were local/ foreign volunteers and NGO community involved in providing assistance to those affected with a range of psychosocial inputs. Sri Lanka Government has also developed mechanisms to provide psychiatry services to those who need, especially by assigning available psychiatrists to visit the districts affected by Tsunami on a weekly basis and building capacity of health workers in providing psychological support to people affected by Tsunami.

Needs assessment questionnaires filled by the families at the community consultation workshops helped us identify the high risk groups that needed immediate attention. Participating at the psychosocial forums organised by both government and NGO sector, was a great opportunity for us to learn the availability of services at the time. The role that we had to play was clear: It was nothing but developing mechanisms and community structures to help psychosocial service providers already available at the time and organising services that were not available.

Psychiatrists assigned by the Ministry of Health and Deputy Provincial Directors – Health Services of Hambantota and Matara districts, requested assistance from BasicNeeds to reach Tsunami affected communities, due to the fact that not many people were attending the mental health clinics organised at the main hospital of the area.

As a result of the discussion, a promotional/advertising programme for mental health services was initiated giving priority to high risk group. Of them about 7.5% were people with mental illnesses:

Community animators and volunteers from affected communities were highly involved in organising mental health clinics at community level covering three components: *Treatment, Mental Health education/promotion and Home visits* to those who are severely ill, having been organised under the psychiatrist who came along with his/her team of registrars and Medical Officer-Mental Health² based in the locality (if available).

2. There are 56 Medical Officers – Mental Health, assigned by the government under a Ministry of Health Scheme since 2001. As a result in some locations the available MOMH joined the team in conducting outreach clinics and then continued the service at hospital from where S/he is based.

Volunteers from the Tsunami affected communities who were trained in identifying high risk groups and in basic Mental Health aspects, along with our community animators, organised group therapy sessions.

Attending to crisis situations like suicide attempts, violent behaviour due to relapses and referrals to hospital based services, etc., were taken charge of by community animators who made home visits to see how the affected people at high risk were getting on. Based on the common issues they learned through these visits, special activities such as psychotherapy /counselling sessions, community education programmes, spiritual activities that help them heal the pain, were organised.

Spiritual activities took a special place in commemorative events where we were involved in assisting and encouraging affected communities who lost their close relatives, to take interest and organise spiritual activities with the belief that, it will add merit to the next life of lost relatives. Special preaching sessions, *Pirith* chanting ceremonies and *Bodhi poojas* as a part of Buddhist Psychotherapy were organised consulting the affected communities under the leadership of volunteers from affected communities throughout the project period, which encouraged them to reduce their grief and recover by the involvement in community activities with a spiritual base.

Relief activities played the greater role during the first three months with high involvement of general public and civil society organisations complementary to the government services in a more informal way. This gave BasicNeeds to develop a volunteer team among the affected communities, so that effective access to services would be assured. By the end of three months, the systems of operations were in place where government took the leadership in monitoring and developing partnership with non-government and private sectors and organising regulatory bodies in place. With the generous funding pouring from non-affected countries and expatriates, organisations and projects evolved in other sectors as well, e.g., livelihoods, health and construction.

As suggested by the communities during consultations, BasicNeeds took the initiative to establish links with other service providers, so that their services are also available to the communities in the areas that we are in operation. In many cases the volunteer committees took the initiative to build links with other service providers:

- Organising eye clinics in collaboration with *Navajeevana, Sunflower village* and Tangalle hospital
- Special maternity clinics organised for pregnant women in collaboration with MOH offices. At these clinics volunteers consulted these women on their priority needs³, for the project to assist

3. All these pregnant women lost all their belongings including the material that they had prepared for child birth, i.e. clothes for the baby, pillow slips, bed sheets, etc., which they usually prepared during the pregnancy. Having lost their interest and being confused, the volunteers proposed the project team to donate items that these women required after the child is born.

- Environmental organisations conducted replanting programmes with the participation of affected children. Drama sessions were organised by Abhina Foundation as a tool to de-traumatise children as well as to build their confidence.

By organising stakeholder workshops for experience sharing, BasicNeeds was able to provide the participating organisations to develop partnership projects, avoiding duplication. It also opened space for participants to clarify unclear areas with the state administrators on regulatory mechanisms introduced by the state.

As part of the normalisation process, community-led psychosocial interventions started from April 2005, as a result of community consultations re-assessing their status – problems, needs and ways of addressing those issues - in groups of women, men, children, youth as well as the elderly:

Community-led special projects/activities to overcome issues/problems identified by affected communities:

As an outcome of children consultation workshops organised by the community animators and volunteers, Children & Youth Clubs were formed and they organised a range of activities with great interest: Adventure camps, Sunday schools, Art competitions, Cultural shows, Quiz programmes, Devotional singing contests, Environmental Day programmes, etc..

Adult members while assisting their children's project were involved in following activities designed by them: Participatory Resource Mapping exercises as a part of skill & needs audit within the affected communities; Skill exchange programme in renovation activities and house to house needs; Spiritual events; Household level expenditure recording and analysing programmes as a preparatory measure to re-occupy themselves in livelihood options.

Children's clubs formed by affected children initiated Sunday Schools for themselves and requested uniforms, which were sewn by the women from affected communities with project assistance. When children from schools in which there were no facilities at all requested material, they were given a task to analyse the problems, work out the solutions and a budget, as part of problem-solving exercise. They were able to propose the solutions with minimum budget where the project had to assist in purchasing basic furniture required. Cleaning of wells was another planned project by the children's clubs during school holidays. They were able to clean about 15 wells so that many families benefited. This project was designed by the children themselves as part of the problem tree exercise they conducted.

Community volunteers were also involved in cleaning a Family Health worker's Office, which was also affected by Tsunami. With their recommendation, the project assisted them in buying plastic chairs and a water filter for the office.

Lessons learned

“We are confused when reasoning out the true cause of Tsunami disaster. However strong the shock that we still experience, I feel Tsunami has forcibly made us see the true picture of life. Even today, if someone says that another tide is coming up we panic; our bodies tremble... it is not easy to recover, even though we know that it is not true. It takes several days or weeks for us to become normal.

However, at a time of mental pressure like that, this programme is like a pain killer for a person suffering from a terrible headache. The soothing feeling we get by being with you, is like pouring cold water on our body in a hot day of summer. We are grateful to all who served us with many offerings... but, for us who were helpless being attacked by Tsunami tide, the biggest gift came from BasicNeeds.”
A community volunteer from Weligama
March 17, 2005 at the Planning Meeting on interventions

The role of different stakeholders ranging from community members to institutional service providers is clearly laid out, and their way of integrated working encouraging interdependence depicts how important resources can be utilized effectively through recognizing the local capacity and capabilities. Interestingly, this team of practitioners was able to conduct an “action research” with a community affected by Tsunami at a time when they were highly traumatized and in grief.

This highly localized model called *Development- oriented Psychosocial Care for Communities Affected by Tsunami* is now implemented in 57 locations in the Southern Province and 5 locations in the Eastern Province of Sri Lanka, involving more than 5,000 families without excluding any member of the community who are interested in taking part.

Taking the lead in their own communities, there are 368 internally displaced members working as volunteers alongside 76 community animators assigned by the project, 4 psychiatrists assigned by the government and 12 field staff of community development organizations⁴ including BasicNeeds, assisted by primary health care staff of Ministry of Health based in the area of operation.

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4. These organizations are the existing partners of BasicNeeds Sri Lanka: *Navajeevana* – champion in community based rehabilitation of people with disabilities; *GIDES* – specialized in social mobilization and micro-credit; Divisional Secretariat of Embilipitiya – Government Administrative Unit in the area and *DEVELOPERS* – group of enthusiastic teachers from the East.

A range of ideas leading to interventions have generated from the affected children, youth, women and men, which contributed to building their confidence to build their own lives facing the challenge of reality. Localised approaches developed in consultation with affected communities, respecting the culture and norms of communities, promote mental health even in the disaster situations i.e. Community-led psychosocial interventions combined with emotional support

Social capital investment with the view to developing the community resource base is found to be essential if sustainability of change is expected. This has also led the service providers to develop community partnership to assure effective delivery of services while encouraging community ownership.

Active participation encouraged through consultation workshops especially in problem solving by the affected communities, accelerates the recovery from trauma in many instances.

Provided with necessary training, community workers / animators could play a great role in providing emotional support through group sessions in disaster situations and identify those who need professional assistance. This approach has contributed to reduce the time and efforts of psychiatrists, so that they could utilise their time in training community animators and primary health care staff. They are more involved at treatment level attending to severely ill people and supervising the Medical Officers – Mental Health.

BasicNeeds

BasicRights

New Initiatives to Mental Health & Development

BasicNeeds is an UK-based international development organisation working in South Asia and Africa. BasicNeeds Sri Lanka was launched in October 2001 to facilitate social integration of people experiencing mental illnesses, without excluding other members of the communities they are living with.

During the onset of Tsunami, BasicNeeds Sri Lanka was working in fifteen (15) GN divisions of five DS divisions in Hambantota, Matara and Ratnapura districts covering a clientele of 1,786 registered for acquiring mental health services facilitated by BasicNeeds in consultation with Southern Provincial Directorate of Health Services and Deputy Provincial Directorates of Matara and Hamabantota. Presently, BasicNeeds has touched eight provinces covering a clientele of more than 2,500 through following field programmes, following BasicNeeds model of *Development-oriented Mental Health Care*:

- South: Mental Health and Development through Community Partnership to promote government mental health services Community-led Psychosocial Interventions with Tsunami affected communities promoting mental health services of government
- Sabaragamuwa: Mental Health and Development through Community Partnership to promote government mental health services
- Uva/Wayamba: Mental Health and Development through Community Partnership to promote government mental health services (World Bank/MOH pilot project)
- East: Community-led Psychosocial Interventions with Tsunami affected communities
- North/Wayamba
- North Central: Improving mental health status of people displaced due to War
- Western: Horticulture Therapy as a tool to improve lives of destitute mentally ill people stranded in Mental Hospital - Angoda

BasicNeeds' Research and Communications programme running in parallel to the field programmes is responsible for identification of issues and extracting experiences & recommendations of project participants at all levels, which is used in two ways:

- To contribute towards policy changes in favour of mentally ill people
- To design, test and prove interventions with community partnership to overcome issues identified

BasicNeeds, playing a role of a catalyst/facilitator has a resource pool of about 500 individuals ranging from village volunteers/community animators to highly experienced professionals of mental health and economic development/ decision makers - having a share of its present work, which is commended both nationally and internationally.

To know more about us:

www.basicneeds.org.uk

